
PERSONALITY TRAITS, RESILIENCE, EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND POSTPARTUM PSYCHOLOGICAL DISTRESS AMONG NURSING MOTHERS OF SECONDARY HOSPITALS IN BENUE NORTH-EAST, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study investigated the influence of personality traits, resilience, emotional intelligence and postpartum psychological distress among nursing mothers of secondary hospitals in Benue North-East Nigeria. A cross sectional survey design was used. A total of 274 nursing mothers with mean age of 28.86 (SD=4.54) years were sampled using simple random probability sampling method and formed the participants for the study. The data for the study were collated using the NovoPsych Five Factor Personality Scale, Wagnild and Young's Resilience Scale, Schutte Self-Report Emotional Intelligence Test, and The Kessler Psychological Distress Scale. Multiple Linear and Standard Multiple Regression analysis were used to test the study hypotheses. Findings showed that there was a significant independent influence of personality traits, resilience, and emotional intelligence on postpartum psychological distress, also there was a significant joint influence of personality traits, resilience, emotional intelligence on postpartum psychological distress. It was concluded that personality traits, resilience and emotional intelligence are significant determinants of postpartum psychological distress among nursing mothers in secondary hospitals in Benue North-East, Nigeria. the study therefore recommended among othersthat, clinicians should design programmes such as periodic mental health assessment geared towards helping nursing mothers manage postpartum distress effectively; routine assessment of the personality traits of pregnant women and new mothers, particularly those with conscientiousness and neuroticism personality traits, to identify those at risk of postpartum psychological distress.

Key Words: Personality Traits, Resilience, Emotional Intelligence, Postpartum Psychological Distress, Nursing Mothers

Background

Early months of childbirth is a period scientifically referred to as postpartum, it is considered a very special time in a woman's life that should be secured with uttermost diligence as it accompanied significant changes in the life of the mothers, which in turn has significant influence on the newborn baby, their families and the society. This period is characterised with emotional transformations, like joy, happiness and even episode marked with extreme sadness, anger and hostility, which may in turn affect the psychological wellbeing of the mother, the newborn baby and the entire family. Mothers also need to adapt to biological, physical, psychological, and social changes that, in most cases occur during the post delivery period. In some cases, however, the changes can lead to mood disorders, which can be harmful not only for the mother's health, but also for the baby (Hwang et al, 2022). This effect may lead to the child developing behavioral, cognitive, emotional, and social development impairments if not given proper attention and care (Shani et al., 2023).

Several personality traits may influence how nursing mothers cope with perception of postpartum psychological distress, as variation in personality and individual difference may interplay a significant role in reactions to situation and hormonal changes and emotional regulation among Nursing Mothers. Personality traits that may play significant roles in the life of a mother in areas such as the ability of Nursing Mothers to bounce back from adversity more effectively. Women with a stable emotional foundation due to dominance of certain traits may be less prone to experiencing extreme mood swings or emotional distress. Emotional stability can contribute to better mental health during the postpartum period among Nursing Mothers. Some personality trait such as having perfectionistic tendencies may contribute to increased stress, as mothers may feel pressure to meet unrealistic standards. More importantly, Nursing Mothers having ability to adapt to new circumstances and roles is essential for new mothers, as those who are more adaptable may find it easier to adjust to the demands of motherhood and cope with unexpected challenges (Meritzell et al., 2022; Puyané et al., 2022).

The relationship between resilience and perception of postpartum psychological distress among Nursing Mothers is a complex and multifaceted one and cannot be over emphasized, resilience, an individual's ability to bounce back and adapt positively in the face of adversity, stress, or challenges has a significant role to play in the perception of postpartum psychological distress, which is a mood disorder that affect women after childbirth (Nieet al., 2023). Resilience is often linked to a strong social support system, among Nursing Mothers who have supportive relationships with family, friends, and healthcare professionals may experience increased resilience, which may buffer against the risk of postpartum psychological distress. Resilient individuals often have a strong sense of self-efficacy, believing in their ability to overcome challenges. This self-confidence may positively influence a mother's perception of her ability to navigate the demands of motherhood and may contribute to lower rates of postpartum psychological distress. Being resilient is associated with skills such as mindfulness and emotional regulation (Guo et al., 2022; Montgomery et al., 2006). Mothers who are able to stay present, manage their emotions, and regulate stress responses may be less prone to developing Postpartum psychological distress.

Similarly, emotional intelligence (EI) plays a significant role in influencing the perception of postpartum psychological distress among Nursing Mothers (Arshadi et al., 2024; Rode, 2016). Emotional intelligence refers to the ability to recognize, understand, and manage one's own emotions and the emotions of others. Emotional intelligence may

influence perception of postpartum psychological distress in many ways affecting the life of the mother and the baby either positively or negatively. Having self-awareness, which is mediated by emotional intelligence, may play a significant role in the life of Nursing Mothers, as individuals with high emotional intelligence are more likely to be aware of their own emotions and understand the reasons behind them. During the postpartum period, women may experience a range of emotions, including joy, sadness, anxiety, and frustration. Being aware of and acknowledging these emotions can help in coping with them effectively (Stylianides et al., 2016).

Thus, the study seeks to understand the interplay among these variables which may yield significant perspectives for designing focused interventions and assistance systems aimed at augmenting maternal welfare throughout the postpartum phase.

Personality Trait and Postpartum Psychological Distress

In quest to understand the influence of Personality Trait and Postpartum Psychological Distress, Asselmann et al. (2020) examined the role of maternal personality and perceived social support for peripartum changes in psychopathological symptoms using a regional-epidemiological sample of 306 women, where depressive, anxiety, and stress symptoms were assessed three times during pregnancy and three times after delivery with the 21-item version of the Depression Anxiety Stress Scale was used, the Big Five personality traits and perceived social support were assessed with the short version of the Big Five Inventory and the Social Support Questionnaire. They reported that less emotionally stable, less conscientious, and less extraverted women and women with lower perceived social support seem to be at increased risk for peripartum psychopathological symptoms and might thus particularly profit from targeted prevention.

In the intellectual quest of Maliszewska et al. (2016) who studied to identify factors increasing or decreasing the risk for postpartum blues, using a sample of 101 women in their first week postpartum. The Edinburgh Postnatal Depression Scale, questions concerning their medical and social status, and psychological tests (the Personality Inventory NEO-FFI, the Mieczysław Plopa and Jan Rostowski Marriage Questionnaire, and the Berlin Social Support Scales) were used. Finding revealed that high level of neuroticism as well as fear of childbirth increased the risk for postpartum blues (OR = 2.17 and OR = 1.30, respectively), while high level of extraversion and better quality of sleep constituted protective factors

Resilience and Postpartum Psychological Distress

In a study of the Resilience and Postpartum Psychological Distress, Baattaiah et al. (2023) examine the relationship between fatigue, sleep quality, resilience, and the risk of PPD development, through a cross-sectional study conducted using online questionnaire distributed to mothers during their postpartum period. The risk of PPD was assessed using the Edinburgh Postnatal Depression Scale (EPDS), postpartum fatigue (PPF) was assessed using the Fatigue Severity Scale (FSS), sleep quality was assessed using the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI), and resilience was assessed using the Brief Resilience Scale (BRS) among 1409 postpartum women were included in the study. They concluded that mothers with higher levels of fatigue, poor sleep quality, and low resilience levels were at high risk of developing PPD recommending that healthcare providers should identify these factors to set better rehabilitation goals to improve overall maternal health.

In another study, Julian et al. (2024) using a cross-sectional design to test three individual-level of resilience resources mastery, self-esteem, and perceived social support

among 2510 low- and middle-income women enrolled after the birth of a baby in a multi-site study of five communities in the United States at approximately 8 weeks postpartum. They reported that higher levels of two personal resilience resources, mastery and self-esteem, reduced the association between prenatal life stressors and early postpartum depressive symptoms in a large, predominantly low-income multi-site community sample. They concluded that individual-level resilience resources are a protective factor in the early postpartum period when maternal adjustment shapes parent and child health outcomes.

Emotional Intelligence and Postpartum Psychological Distress

In a quest to uncover the influence of Emotional Intelligence and perception of Postpartum Psychological Distress, (Rode, 2016) examined the direct and moderating effects of emotional intelligence on postpartum depression (PPD), while taking into account social support and stressful life events, using a prospective cohort design, with 165 women took part in the surveyed in their third trimester and again at 9 weeks postpartum. Finding revealed that direct effects of emotional intelligence, social support has negatively influence intelligence on postpartum depression, while stressful life events has positive influence on PPD. Moderating effects were also supported with significant effects on PPD with stressful life events \times emotional intelligence and stressful life events \times social support. It was concluded that emotional intelligence and social support are buffers against postpartum stress as against stressful life events.

Relatedly, Çankaya, & Ataş, (2022) assess the effects of cognitive emotion regulation, emotional intelligence status and related factors on postpartum depression (PPD) among 268 postpartum women with babies aged 1–12 months in pediatric outpatient clinic of the Medical Faculty Hospital of a province in the Central Anatolian Region of Turkey. They reported that about 71 (26.5 %) mothers received scores above the cut-off point in the depression scale. Experiencing emotional violence, having cognitive emotion regulation difficulties, and low emotional intelligence characteristics affected the risk of developing postpartum depression. It was concluded that exposure to emotional violence, cognitive emotion regulation, and poor emotional intelligence status reveal that they are important in identifying women at risk of PPD.

Hypotheses

- i. Personality Traits will significantly predict Postpartum Psychological Distress among Nursing Mothers of secondary hospitals, in Benue North-East, Nigeria.
- ii. Resilience will significantly predict Postpartum Psychological Distress among Nursing Mothers of secondary hospitals, in Benue North-East, Nigeria.
- iii. Emotional Intelligence will significantly predict Postpartum Psychological Distress among Nursing Mothers of secondary hospitals, in Benue North-East, Nigeria.

Design

This study employed the use of a cross-sectional survey design. This type of design involves the collection of data from a relatively large number of participants to make inferences about a population of interest at one point in time. This method is most suitable for this research because, it allows the researcher to sample a large number of Nursing Mothers, collect data through questionnaire in such that inferences are made about their Postpartum Psychological Distress, a post childbirth condition and whether or not it is predicted by psychological attributes of personality traits, resilience, and emotional intelligence. The independent variables in the study are personality traits, resilience and emotional intelligence while postpartum psychological distress was used as dependent variable.

Population

The researcher wrote all the names of the seven local government areas on pieces of papers, folded and placed in a bowl, and randomly handpicked four pieces of papers which contained Ushongo, Logo, Katsina ala and Vandeikya local government areas as used in the study. The study population consisted of 336 nursing mothers who are currently attending Postnatal Care (PNC) at General Hospital Lessel (76), General Hospital Ugba (82), General Hospital Katsina Ala (97) and General Hospital Vandeikya (81) all in the Benue North-East.

Sample size Determination

The researcher used the Krejcie and Morgan sample size determining table for finite population (Shindi, 2017).

Sampling Technique

The researcher adopted the simple random probability sampling technique to sample participants for the study. The simple random probability sampling technique avails every participant equal opportunity to participate, this technique was used because the researcher considered all participants that meet the criteria and accepted participating in the study to do so (Cochran, 1963).

Participants

The study participants consist of 274 nursing mothers receiving Postnatal Care (PNC) at General Hospital Lessel-Ushongo, General Hospital Ugba-Logo, General Hospital Katsina ala and General Hospital Vandeikya, all in the Benue North-East. From the sample size estimation table, a total number of 274 samples were used for the study as follows: General hospital Lessel, Ugba, Katsina Ala and Vandeikya have 63, 66, 76 and 69 participants respectively. Participants were sampled according to the population for each hospital independently using Krejiac and Morgan sample size estimation table for finite population, and summed to get the total numbers of participants.

Instruments

Four instruments were used for this study. These are:

- i) **The NovoPsych Five Factor Personality Scale 30 (NFFPS-30):** The NovoPsych Five Factor Personality Scale 30 developed by Buchanan & Hegarty, (2023) is a shortened version of the IPIP-NEO-120. The IPIP-NEO-120 is a product of the International Personality Item Pool collaboration project (IPIP; Goldberg *et al.* 2006) and is a publicly available representation of the five factor measurement model (Johnson, 2014), drawing 120 items from the International Personality Item Pool (IPIP; Goldberg *et al.* 2006) was develop to assess personality characteristics. According to Buchanan and Hegarty, (2023), the NFFPS-30 has good reliability coefficient, result from their test of the NFFPS-30 reliability were as follows: Openness to Experience: $r = 0.86$; Conscientiousness: $r = 0.93$; Extraversion: $r = 0.90$; Agreeableness: $r = 0.89$ Neuroticism: $r = 0.93$; with overall reliability coefficient of $\alpha = >.80$
- ii) **Wagnild and Young's Resilience Scale (RS-14):** Resilience Scale (RS)-14 was developed by Gail, Wagnild and Young (1993) to measure resilience among the general population, the scale has also been validated on Nigerian population returning high psychometric properties (Abiola, & Udofia, 2011). The scale has 14 items scored on 7 response Likert scale ranging from 1 =strongly disagree; 2 =mostly disagree; 3 =somewhat disagree; 4 =neither agree nor disagree; 5 =somewhat agree; 6 =mostly agree; and 7 =strongly agree. All items are worded positively and possible scores range

from 25 to 175, with higher scores reflecting higher levels of resilience (Wagnild & Young, 1993). The scale has a Cronbach's alpha reliability of RS-14 has been reported at 0.83 (Damasio, Borsa & da Silva, 2011) and 0.90 (Aiena *et al.* 2014).

- iii) Schutte Self-Report Emotional Intelligence Test (SSEIT):** The Schulte Self-Report Emotional Intelligence Test (SSEIT) is a standardise test that is used for measuring general Emotional Intelligence (EI) developed by Schutte *et al.* (1998), using four sub-scales: emotion perception, utilizing emotions, managing self- relevant emotions, and managing others' emotions with items for perception of emotion including items 5, 8, 9, 15, 18, 25, 27, 29, and 32; managing own emotions 3, 21, 22, 28, and 31; managing others' emotions 1, 11, 24, and 26; utilization of emotion 17, 20, and 23; while uncatagorized items include 2, 4, 6, 7, 10, 12, 13, 14, 16, 19, 30, 33. Salovey and Mayer (1990) structure the SSEIT off the EI model. The test has an internal consistency, which refers to the extent to which the items on a test measure the same construct of about 0.90 coefficient. The SSEIT has good test-retest reliability, with a correlation coefficient of 0.78 (Austin *et al.* 2004; Schulte *et al.* 1998).
- iv) The Kessler Psychological Distress Scale (K10):** A standardise measure of psychological distress developed by Kessler *et al.* (2003) with ten items measuring emotional states each with a five-level response scale. The measure can be used as a brief screen to identify levels of distress. The tool can be given to patients to complete, or alternatively the questions can be read to the patient by the practitioner. Scoring instructions each item is scored from one 'none of the time' to five 'all of the time'. Scores of the 10 items are then summed, yielding a minimum score of 10 and a maximum score of 50. Low scores indicate low levels of psychological distress and high scores indicate high levels of psychological distress. The 2000 Collaborative Health and Well-Being Survey were used to test reliability of the K10. The kappa and weighted kappa scores ranged from 0.42 to 0.74, indicating that the K10 is a moderately reliable instrument. Although supplementary research on the clinical cut-off times and the scoring are needed to determine psychological distress, the K10 is a brief, simple, and reliable instrument to detect mental health conditions in the population.

Procedure

A letter of introduction was obtained from the Department of Psychology Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi and presented for study permission and approval from Benue State Hospitals Management Board. After obtaining an approval from the Board, the researcher proceeded to register with the Research Ethical Committee of the selected health facility for onward approval for the data collection at each facility. Thereafter the nursing mothers attending postnatal care in the Health Care facilities were identify and dully consented to participate in the study. Those who were willing to participate were guided to complete the research questionnaire in the immunization halls of the hospitals. Two trained nurses and midwives assisted in the administration of the questionnaire in each of the Health Care facility as instructed by the researcher. Thereafter, completed questionnaires were collected after completion and sorted out to ensure that only those that are accurately responded to were processed for data analysis. The whole process of administration and retrieval of the questionnaire lasted for two weeks.

Data Analyses

Data collected for this study was analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics; for test of psychometric properties of the study instruments, a correlational statistic

(Cronbach's Alpha) was used to test the reliability of the instruments. For test of hypotheses, multiple linear regression analysis was used to find out the independent influence of Resilience, Emotional Intelligence, on Postpartum Psychological Distress. Lastly, the multiple linear regression analysis was used to determine the influence of Personality Traits and its dimension which was conducted using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) data analysis software.

Results

Table 1: Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Showing Influence of Personality Traits on Postpartum Psychological Distress Among Nursing Mothers of secondary hospitals, In Benue North-East, Nigeria

Predictors	R	R ²	Df	F	β	t	P
Constant	.423	.162	5,248	10.780			.000
Openness to Experience					-.082	-.067	.946
Conscientiousness					2.228	2.635	.009
Extraversion					-1.109	-1.415	.158
Agreeableness					-1.269	-1.424	.156
Neuroticism					.512	6.365	.000

Dependent Variable: Postpartum Psychological Distress

The result presented in table 4.1 above revealed that, the overall model is significant showing that personality traits significantly impact postpartum psychological distress among nursing mothers [$R=.423$, $R^2=.162$, $F(5,248)= 10.780$, $p<.01$]. The result further revealed that the personality trait accounted about 42.3% of the total variance observed in postpartum psychological distress among Nursing Mothers.

However, further observations of the result showed that among all the traits examined, Conscientiousness ($\beta=2.228$, $t=2.635$, $p<.05$); Neuroticism ($\beta=.512$, $t=6.365$, $p<.001$) significantly and positively contributed to the model, this implies that as mothers become more conscientious and neurotic in trait, the chances of developing postpartum psychological distress increases while Openness to Experience ($\beta=-.082$, $t=-.067$, $p>.05$); Extraversion ($\beta=-1.109$, $t=-1.415$, $p>.05$) and Agreeableness ($\beta=-1.269$, $t=-1.424$, $p>.05$), did not make any significant contribution to the model respectively. Based on this result, hypothesis one is accepted.

Table 2: Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Showing Influence of Resilience on Postpartum Psychological Distress Among Nursing Mothers of secondary hospitals, In Benue North-East, Nigeria

Predictors	R	R ²	Df	F	β	T	P
Constant	.387	.150	2,260	22.860			.000
Low Resilience					.610	6.657	.000
High Resilience					-3.073	-2.121	.035

Dependent Variable: Postpartum Psychological Distress

The result presented in table 4.2 above revealed that, there is a significant influence of resilience on postpartum psychological distress among nursing mothers [R=.387, R²=.150, F(2,260)= 22.860, p<.01]. The result further revealed that the resilience accounted about 38.7% of the total variance observed in postpartum psychological distress among Nursing Mothers

However, further observations of the result for independent contribution showed that high resilience (β =-3.073, t=-2.121, p<.05) significantly negatively contributed to the model, implying that mothers who are high on resilience skill has a decrease in postpartum psychological distress symptoms, while low resilience (β =.610, t=6.657, p>.01) significantly positively contributed to the model, implying that mothers who are low on resilience skill has corresponding an increase in postpartum psychological distress symptoms. Based on this result, hypothesis two is also accepted

Table 3: Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Showing Influence of Emotional Intelligence on Postpartum Psychological Distress Among Nursing Mothers of secondary hospitals, In Benue North-East, Nigeria

Predictors	R	R ²	Df	F	β	t	P
Constant	.566	.321	2,271	64.016			.000
High Emotional Intelligence					-.347	-.291	.771
Low Emotional Intelligence					.494	11.311	.000

Dependent Variable: Postpartum Psychological Distress

The result presented in table 4.3 above revealed a significant regression model, showing that there is a significant influence of emotional intelligence on postpartum psychological distress among nursing mothers [R=.566, R²=.321, F(2,271)= 64.016, p<.01]. The result further revealed that emotional intelligence accounted about 56.6% of the total variance observed in postpartum psychological distress among Nursing Mothers.

However, further observations of the result showed that among all the variables examined, only low emotional intelligence (β =.294, t=11.311, p<.01) significantly contributed to the model, this infers that nursing mothers who have low scores on emotional intelligence has corresponding increase in postpartum psychological distress. Whereas mothers who scored high on emotional intelligence (β =-.347, t=-.291, p>.05), did not make significant contribution to the model respectively. However, based on this result, hypothesis three was accepted since the regression model was significant.

Discussion of Findings

Hypothesis one stated that personality traits will significantly predict postpartum psychological distress among Nursing Mothers of secondary hospitals, in Benue North-East, Nigeria. The result showed that personality traits is a significant predictor of postpartum psychological distress among Nursing Mothers. This finding is proportioned to the findings of Asselmann et al. (2020) who examined the role of maternal personality and perceived social support for peripartum changes in psychopathological symptoms using a regional-epidemiological sample of 306 women, reporting that less emotionally stable, less conscientious, and less extraverted women and women with lower perceived social support seem to be at increased risk for peripartum psychopathological symptoms and might thus particularly profit from targeted prevention. Findings from the present study also is in agreement with the study of Roman et al. (2019) who investigated personality traits and postnatal depression 2 weeks after giving birth among six hundred and seventy-two new mothers and found out that personality traits of neuroticism and consciousness, in the natural birth's group, and neuroticism and agreeableness, in the cesarean births group, were associated with postnatal depression. Relatedly, the study collaborates that of Maryami et al. (2020) who examined the role of social support and personality in the incidence of postpartum depression among two hundred mothers referred to health centers by available sampling method between 6 weeks to 6 months after delivery and reported presence of Postpartum Psychological Distress was observed in 49 (24.5%) of mothers with mothers with neuroticism having the highest relationship with postpartum depression. More so, finding from hypothesis one agrees with the study of Murakami et al. (2022) who reported that personality is a significant predictor of postpartum depressive symptoms (PDS) among 15,012 women in the Tohoku Medical Megabank Project Birth and Three-Generation Cohort Study reporting high prevalence of postpartum distress after one month of delivery was 13.1% with higher neuroticism scores were associated with PDS, lower extraversion scores were associated with PDS.

Hypothesis two which stated that resilience will significantly predict postpartum psychological distress among Nursing Mothers of secondary hospitals, in Benue North-East, Nigeria. The result showed that resilience is a significant predictor of postpartum psychological distress among Nursing Mothers. Finding from the present study agrees with the study of Baattaiah et al. (2023) who examined the relationship between fatigue, sleep quality, resilience, and the risk of postpartum distress development, through a cross-sectional study conducted among 1409 mothers during their postpartum period. among postpartum women and concluded that mothers with higher levels of fatigue, poor sleep quality, and low resilience levels were at high risk of developing postpartum distress recommending that healthcare providers should identify these factors to set better rehabilitation goals to improve overall maternal health. More so findings from the present study collaborate with the study of Sexton et al. (2015) who investigated main and moderating influences of resilience and childhood history of maltreatment on posttraumatic stress disorder (PTSD), major depressive disorder (MDD), parental sense of mastery, and family functioning among 214 mothers and reported that mothers with highest resilience did not met the criteria for postpartum MDD, irrespective of childhood trauma, while for those with lowest quartile of resilience, reported severity in depression and distress. Furthermore, findings from the present study supported that of Mautner et al. (2022) who studied resilience differences in postpartum depression after admission of newborns at the neonatal intensive care unit at a teaching hospital in Austria among sixty women and concluded that mothers with lower resilience are susceptible to postpartum distress and would benefit from social support and emotional health-promoting activities to improve their psychological health. In another intellectual quest, Baattaiah,

Alharbi, & Babteen, (2023) examined several factors that contribute to the development of postpartum depression (PPD) and negatively affect mothers' mental and physical well-being using a cross-sectional study was conducted using an online questionnaire distributed to mothers during their postpartum period and concluded that mothers with higher levels of fatigue, poor sleep quality, and low resilience levels were at high risk of developing postpartum depression, a form of postpartum psychological distress.

Lastly, finding from hypothesis three which stated that emotional intelligence will significantly predict postpartum psychological distress among Nursing Mothers of secondary hospitals, in Benue North-East, Nigeria. The result showed that emotional intelligence is a significant predictor of postpartum psychological distress among Nursing Mothers. This finding support Rode, (2016) who examined the direct and moderating effects of emotional intelligence on postpartum depression (PPD), social support and stressful life events among 165 women and reported a negative effects of emotional intelligence and social support on postpartum depression, while stressful life events had positive influence on PPD, they concluded that been highly emotional intelligent with quality social support are buffers against postpartum stress as against stressful life events. Relatedly, this finding support the study of Çankaya, & Ataş, (2022) who assess the effects of cognitive emotion regulation, emotional intelligence status and related factors on postpartum depression (PPD) among 268 postpartum women with babies in pediatric outpatient clinic of the Medical Faculty Hospital of a province in the Central Anatolian Region of Turkey. Elsewhere the present findings validated the study of Sahin, & Sogukpinar, (2023) who evaluated the relationship between emotional intelligence and postpartum depression risk and the factors affecting it at Katip Çelebi University Atatürk Training and Research Hospital, Obstetrics Clinic among 193 women who delivered at the Katip Çelebi University Atatürk Training and Research Hospital's Obstetrics Clinic, and reported a non-statistically significant relationship between postpartum depression risk and emotional intelligence, whilst reporting a statistically significant relationship between postpartum depression risk and relationships with spouse and marital satisfaction. Furthermore, this finding collaborate Rabbani, (2020) who investigated emotional intelligence and marital satisfaction and their relationship to postpartum depression among postpartum women at Hafez Hospital in Shiraz among 147 postpartum women, revealing that quality emotional intelligence, and marital satisfaction had a significant negative correlation with postpartum depression, inferencing that that increased emotional intelligence and marital satisfaction could reduce the level of postpartum depression.

Recommendations

Based on findings of the study, it was recommended that;

- i. Healthcare providers should ensure routine assessment of the personality traits of pregnant women and new mothers, particularly those with conscientiousness and neuroticism personality traits, to identify those at risk of postpartum psychological distress.
- ii. Resilience building interventions should be integrated into prenatal and postnatal care to help mothers develop good coping skills that may moderate the risk of postpartum psychological distress.
- iii. Emotional intelligence enhancement programs should be developed and implemented to help nursing mothers manage their emotions, empathize with others, and develop effective coping strategies.
- iv. A multidisciplinary approach involving obstetricians, psychologists, social workers, and nurses should be adopted to provide comprehensive care and support to nursing mothers.

Contribution to Knowledge

This study contributes significantly to the existing body of knowledge on postpartum psychological distress among nursing mothers. The findings provide new insights into the roles personality traits, resilience, and emotional intelligence in predicting postpartum psychological distress. Based on finding the following were observed as contribution to knowledge from the study for clinical practice and research purposes; specifically:

- i. This study finding that conscientiousness and neuroticism traits are significant predictors of postpartum psychological distress among nursing mothers contributes to the understanding of the relationship between personality traits and postpartum psychological distress. This knowledge can inform the development of targeted interventions aimed at mitigating the effects of these traits on postpartum psychological distress.
- ii. Secondly, the study finding that resilience is a significant predictor of postpartum psychological distress among nursing mothers highlights the importance of resilience in mitigating the risk of postpartum psychological distress. This knowledge can inform the development of resilience-building interventions aimed at reducing the risk of postpartum psychological distress.
- iii. Furthermore, the study finding that emotional intelligence is a significant predictor of postpartum psychological distress among nursing mothers contributes to the understanding of the relationship between emotional intelligence and postpartum psychological distress. This knowledge can inform the development of emotional intelligence enhancement programs aimed at reducing the risk of postpartum psychological distress.

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